

1 **The effect of gravity of the plastic zones on the behavior of supports in very deep tunnels**
2 **excavated in rock masses**

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13 **ABSTRACT**

14 The vertical load acting on a support structure is affected by the loss of self-bearing capacity of
15 the rock inside the plastic zone. This load can then be accounted for by analytical calculation
16 methods capable of evaluating the stresses in the tunnel support system to proceed with the tunnel
17 design. Generally, the effect of the rock's own weight in the plastic zone is considered in a
18 simplistic way by evaluating an additional vertical load given by the weight of the rock due to the
19 thickness of the plastic zone. This approach leads to a significant increase in the vertical load with
20 the risk of overdesigning the support structure. In this work, the effect of the rock's own weight in
21 the plastic zone was considered by modifying the numerical solution of the convergence-
22 confinement method for tunnels built in rock. In this way, through the intersection of the

23 characteristic curve of the tunnel and the intersection line of the support structure, it is possible to
24 determine both the vertical loads (with the effect of the weight of the rock) and the horizontal load
25 (without the effect of weight of the rock). The application of the method to a project in the Alps
26 allowed to detect the magnitude of the percentage increase of the vertical load and a significant
27 increase in the thickness of the plastic zone with the consequences that this may have on the
28 designing of the radial bolting length in that zone. Increasing the plastic radius leads to an increase
29 in the length of the bolts. This is interesting because in the area of the crown where the weight of
30 the plasticized rock is considered the bolts are usually installed with a greater length. In the final
31 part of the paper a new procedure is illustrated to define the vertical and horizontal loads acting on
32 the support structures, starting from the convergence-confinement curves, obtained for the crown
33 and for the lateral areas (sides).

34 **KEY WORDS:** convergence-confinement method; hyperstatic reaction method; base tunnel;
35 plastic radius; rock

36

37 **ABBREVIATIONS AND NOTATION LIST**

- 38 a exponent of the failure criterion of Hoek and Brown
- 39 A_s area of the lining section
- 40 D parameter that varies between 0 and 1, which considers the disturbance of the rock mass
- 41 due to the excavation operations
- 42 E_r elastic modulus of the rock mass in the plastic field
- 43 F_n limit strength of the elastic-plastic behavior of the normal springs
- 44 f_r component of body forces per unit volume in the radial direction
- 45 f_θ component of body forces per unit volume in the tangential directions
- 46 I_s inertia moment along the lining section
- 47 k stiffness of the lining
- 48 K_n stiffness of the normal interaction springs
- 49 K_s stiffness of the shear interaction springs
- 50 k_0 earth pressure at rest
- 51 M bending moments along the support
- 52 m_b strength parameter, which depend on the GSI (Geological Strength Index)
- 53 m_i strength parameter that refers to intact rock and which depends on the typology of the rock
- 54 N normal forces along the support

- 55 p pressure inside the tunnel
- 56 p_{cr} critical pressure
- 57 p_0 natural lithostatic stress at the tunnel depth
- 58 r_0 tunnel radius
- 59 R_{pl} plastic radius
- 60 s strength parameter, which depend on the GSI (Geological Strength Index)
- 61 u_{crown} support displacements at the crown of the tunnel
- 62 u_R radial displacement
- 63 u_{sides} support displacements at the sides of the tunnel
- 64 $\varphi_{res,app}$ apparent residual friction angle of the rock mass
- 65 σ_{Rpl} radial stress at the plastic radius
- 66 σ_r radial stress
- 67 $\sigma_{R,crown}$ vertical load applied at the crown of the support
- 68 $\sigma_{R,sides}$ horizontal load applied at the side of the support
- 69 $\sigma_{r,i}$ incremental radial stress
- 70 $\sigma_{\theta,i}$ incremental tangential stress
- 71 σ_θ tangential stress
- 72 σ_1 principal maximum stress

- 73 $\sigma_{1,lim}$ maximum principle stress upon failure of the rock mass
- 74 σ_3 principal minimum stress
- 75 $\tau_{R\theta}$ shear stress
- 76 θ angle representing the evaluation point in the circular support in the tunnel
- 77 γ weight of the rock
- 78 ψ dilatancy expressed in radians
- 79 ν Poisson ratio of the rock mass
- 80 CC Characteristic curve
- 81 CCM Convergence-confinement method
- 82 GSI Geological Strength Index
- 83 HRM Hyperstatic reaction method

84 **INTRODUCTION**

85 Determination of the stresses and displacements around circular openings has been one of the most
86 fundamental problems in geotechnical, petroleum, and mining engineering. Design of tunnel liners
87 and the validation of numerical models are among the practical applications of displacement
88 analysis around circular openings. The most common support design techniques are based on
89 analytical approaches, such as the hyperstatic reaction method, HRM (Do et al., 2014a; Oreste et
90 al., 2018a; 2018b) and the Einstein and Schwartz (1979) method. However, these analytical
91 methods require knowledge of the loads acting on the support structures. The loads depend on:

- 92 • The dimension and depth of the tunnel;
- 93 • The geomechanical characteristics of the ground;
- 94 • The stiffness characteristics of the support structure itself and;
- 95 • The distance from the excavation face where the structure is to be installed.

96 Interaction between the rock mass and the support system is generally evaluated with the
97 convergence-confinement method (CCM). CCM describes the relation between the decreasing
98 tunnel internal pressure and the increasing tunnel radial convergence and can be constructed from
99 elasto-plastic analysis of a circular tunnel subjected to hydrostatic far-field stress and uniform
100 internal pressure (see Panet, 1995; Peila and Oreste, 1995; Oreste, 2009; 2014; Spagnoli et al.,
101 2016; 2017). CCM allows to obtain an estimate of the loads acting on the supporting structures,
102 proceeding with the intersection of the ground characteristic curve of the tunnel and the
103 characteristic curve of the supporting structure.

104 In the base tunnels in rocks, the extension of the plastic zone around the tunnel may be significant,
105 above all when the GSI value is low, the strength of the intact rock is reduced, the tunnel radius is

106 high and the lithostatic pressure is high. The development of an adequate plastic zone is, however,
107 necessary also to be able to contain the loads on the supporting works. Rock with plastic behavior
108 loses a significant part of its resistance and does not generally have the ability to self-sustain itself.
109 For this reason, it is prudent in the design phase, to consider the rock with plastic behavior in the
110 calculation of the applied loads to the support system with its own weight.

111 A large body of work currently exists on the stress and deformation analysis of tunnels with the
112 consideration of different failure criteria and rock mass behaviors including the elastic-perfectly
113 plastic, elastic-brittle-plastic and elastic-strain-softening models (e.g., Brown et al., 1983;
114 Carranza-Torres and Fairhurst, 1999; Carranza-Torres, 2004; Alonso et al., 2003; Park and Kim,
115 2006; Lee and Pietruszczak, 2008; Park et al., 2008; Fahimifar and Hedayat, 2008; 2009; Fahimifar
116 et al., 2010; Hedayat, 2016). CCM is also applied to rock masses, presenting a non-linear rupture
117 criterion, as described by Hoek and Brown (1980).

118 In the present work a procedure to obtain the characteristic curve of the tunnel considering the
119 effect of the rock weight in the plastic zone is presented. An example of a calculation, relating to
120 a tunnel built in the Alps will allow to evaluate the weight of the rock in the plasticized zone on
121 the loads acting on the support. The final analysis with HRM will allow to detect the importance
122 of the additional load on the tension state that develops in the support work and, therefore, on the
123 stability conditions of the support itself.

124 **THE CONVERGENCE-CONFINEMENT METHOD CONSIDERING GRAVITY EFFECT**

125 When the internal pressure in tunnels falls below a critical pressure, p_{cr} , a plastic zone develops
126 around the tunnel. The tunnel conditions typically assumed for elasto-plastic analysis include a
127 deep circular tunnel in a continuous, homogeneous, isotropic, and initially elastic rock mass
128 subjected to the hydrostatic far-field stress.

129 In base tunnels with high overburden pressure, the initial stress state of the rock mass generally
130 approaches the hydrostatic conditions (k_0 is approximately equal to 1). As the internal pressure
131 decreases, the tunnel radial convergence increases. Brown et al. (1983) summarized a large number
132 of solutions obtained for an axisymmetric tunnel problem and presented a closed-form solution for
133 rocks with elastic-brittle plastic behavior as well as a step-wise sequence of calculations for rock
134 with an elastic-strain-softening behavior. Wang (1996) improved the accuracy of the solution in
135 predicting the plastic radius. Carranza-Torres (2004) proposed a rigorous, elasto-plastic solution
136 by rewriting the generalized Hoek-Brown failure criterion in terms of transformed stress quantities.

137 In the present work a detailed analysis method of CC for rock tunnels will be employed, based on
138 a numerical solution to finite differences (Oreste, 2014). The rock around the tunnel is subdivided
139 into several thin concentric rings, in which the values of apparent cohesion and of the apparent
140 friction angle are continuously determined, linearizing the Hoek-Brown strength criterion
141 according to the value of the radial tension reached. The dilatancy is determined for each
142 concentric ring, as a predefined percentage of the apparent residual friction angle of the specific
143 ring considered. The calculation is repeated for each concentric ring, varying the internal pressure
144 acting on the perimeter of the tunnel. Provided that the inner pressure falls below a critical pressure,
145 p_{cr} , a plastic region of radius R_{pl} develops around the tunnel. Because the dead weight of the broken
146 zone around the tunnel can significantly increase the required support pressure at the roof, the
147 effect of gravity must be considered in the interaction between the ground and the support system.

148 In other words, the dead weight of the broken zone exerts higher pressures to the support system
149 at the crown of the tunnel and needs to be considered in the elasto-plastic analysis of the tunnel. It
150 is suggested that the readers refer to Oreste (2014) for more detailed information. Limited work
151 has been conducted on the effect of the gravitational forces acting on the ground (Hoek and Brown,

152 1980; Detournay, 1984; Panet 1995; Zareifard and Fahimifar, 2012). To account for the gravity
 153 effect, Hoek and Brown (1980) and Panet (1995) suggested an increase in the required support
 154 pressure by the amount of $\gamma(R_{pl} - r_0)$, where γ is the unit weight of the rock and r_0 is the tunnel
 155 radius. This adjustment assumes that the full weight of the broken zone at the tunnel crown will
 156 be transferred to the support system, resulting in ground response curves that are too conservative.
 157 Therefore, there is a critical need to study the true interaction between the ground and the
 158 supporting system. The weight of the broken zone around the tunnel can be so high that it may
 159 affect the tunnel stability. The most critical point is the tunnel crown and the stability assessment
 160 needs to be carried out by the construction of the ground response curve at the crown.

161 Assuming a state of hydrostatic stress field and plane strain condition around a circular tunnel, the
 162 equilibrium equations in the radial and tangential directions taking the gravity forces into account
 163 are defined by assessing the stress state. Consider a small element ABCD shown in Fig. 1, since
 164 the tunnel problem is under plane strain condition, all stress components are functions of radial
 165 and tangential directions. Hence, it is possible to use polar coordinate instead of cylindrical one.
 166 Let f_r and f_θ be the components of the body forces per unit volume in radial and tangential
 167 directions, respectively (see Fig. 1).

168 Summation of forces parallel to the radial direction through the center of element yields:

$$\begin{aligned}
 169 \quad & \left(\sigma_r + \frac{\partial \sigma_r}{\partial r} dr \right) (r + dr) d\theta - \sigma_r r d\theta - \left[\sigma_\theta + \frac{\partial \sigma_\theta}{\partial \theta} d\theta - \sigma_\theta \right] dr \sin \frac{d\theta}{2} + \left[\tau_{r\theta} + \frac{\partial \tau_{r\theta}}{\partial \theta} d\theta - \right. \\
 170 \quad & \left. \tau_{r\theta} \right] dr \cos \frac{d\theta}{2} + f_r r dr d\theta = 0 \tag{1}
 \end{aligned}$$

171 Since $d\theta$ is infinitesimal, $\sin \frac{d\theta}{2}$ and $\cos \frac{d\theta}{2}$ can be replaced by $\frac{d\theta}{2}$ and unity, respectively.
 172 Neglecting the small quantities of higher order and dividing the above equation by $r dr d\theta$, the
 173 equation of equilibrium in radial direction can be found as follows:

174
$$\frac{\partial \sigma_r}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \tau_{r\theta}}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\sigma_r - \sigma_\theta}{r} + f_r = 0 \quad (2)$$

175 Similarly, summation of tangential components of forces may result in the equilibrium equation
 176 in direction.

177
$$\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \sigma_\theta}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial \tau_{r\theta}}{\partial r} + \frac{2\tau_{r\theta}}{r} + f_\theta = 0 \quad (3)$$

178 As the mentioned tunnel problem has axial symmetry, the radial and tangential stresses in the rock
 179 mass will be principal stresses (i.e. $\sigma_r = \sigma_3$ and $\sigma_\theta = \sigma_1$) and consequently the radial equilibrium
 180 equations can be reduced to:

181
$$\frac{\partial \sigma_r}{\partial r} + \frac{\sigma_r - \sigma_\theta}{r} + f_r = 0 \quad (4)$$

182 In above equation, f_r is the component of body forces per unit volume in the radial direction. Since
 183 the construction of ground response curve at the roof of the tunnel, which is the most critical point,
 184 is of great importance, γ , unit weight of the rock mass, must be substituted for f_r in the equilibrium
 185 equation. In fact, at the roof of the tunnel, the gravity forces per unit volume are radially toward
 186 the tunnel center and are equal to γ . Thus, the equilibrium equation within the broken zone can be
 187 rewritten as:

188
$$\frac{\partial \sigma_r}{\partial r} + \frac{\sigma_r - \sigma_\theta}{r} + \gamma = 0 \quad (5)$$

189 Fig. 2a demonstrates schematically the body forces acting at the roof of the tunnel according to
 190 equation (4). Figure 2b shows the graphical representation of the theoretical ground response curve
 191 at the roof with and without consideration of the gravity effect from the plastic zone. The ABC
 192 curve represents the ground response curve without consideration of the gravity forces while curve
 193 ABMD demonstrates the ground response curve with consideration of gravity forces. The curve
 194 ABMD represents comparably larger values of convergence at a given internal pressure. The
 195 existence of a minimum M in the ground response curve shows the importance of the dead weight
 196 of the broken zone compared with the in situ stresses.

197 Zareifard and Fahimifar (2012) developed an interesting elasto-plastic, analytical-numerical
198 solution, which considers the curvilinear strength criterion of the previous solution of Hoek and
199 Brown (1988). This solution applies to a strain-softening behavior of the rock and links some
200 fundamental rock parameters in the plastic field to the actual deviatoric plastic strain and to the
201 critical value of the deviatoric plastic strain. In order to represent the rock behavior correctly,
202 sophisticated laboratory tests are necessary in order to define in detail the parameters required by
203 the adopted behavior model. Taking into account that the solution of Zareifard and Fahimifar
204 (2012) does not consider the updated generalized failure criterion (i.e. Hoek et al., 2002), equation
205 6 has also been used in the numerical procedure formulated by Oreste (2014), in order to obtain
206 the description of the CC of the tunnel considering the effect of the weight of the plastic zone
207 around the tunnel. Besides, regarding the dilatation of the rock mass (difficult to evaluate in the
208 laboratory), this is linked in the proposed procedure to the residual friction angle of the rock mass,
209 as a fixed percentage of the latter.

210 **THE PROPOSED NUMERICAL MODEL**

211 The last update of the failure criterion of Hoek and Brown (Hoek et al., 2002) for rock masses has
212 the following expression:

$$213 \quad \sigma_{1,lim} = \sigma_3 + \sigma_{ci} \cdot \left(m_b \cdot \frac{\sigma_3}{\sigma_{ci}} + s \right)^a \quad (6)$$

214 where: $\sigma_{1,lim}$ is the maximum principle stress upon failure of the rock mass;

215 σ_3 is the minimum principle stress (confinement);

216 σ_{ci} is the uniaxial compression strength (UCS) of the intact rock;

217 m_b and s are the strength parameters, which depend on the GSI (Geological Strength Index)
 218 (Marinos and Hoek, 2000; Marinos et al., 2005) and on the parameter D :

$$219 \quad m_b = m_i \cdot e^{\left(\frac{GSI-100}{28-14 \cdot D}\right)}; \quad s = e^{\left(\frac{GSI-100}{9-3 \cdot D}\right)}$$

220 D is a parameter that varies between 0 and 1, which considers the disturbance of the rock
 221 mass due to the excavation operations ($D=0$ for non-disturbed mass; $D=1$ for intensely
 222 disturbed mass);

223 m_i is a strength parameter that refers to intact rock and which depends on the typology of
 224 the rock;

$$225 \quad a \text{ is the exponent that is present in eq. 6: } a = 0.5 + \frac{1}{6} \cdot \left(e^{-\frac{GSI}{15}} - e^{-\frac{20}{3}} \right).$$

226 For the good and medium-quality rock masses exhibiting a fragile elasto-plastic behavior it is
 227 necessary to describe two failure criteria, one for the peak conditions and another for the residual
 228 conditions. The former governs the stress state in the rock mass at the elastic limit, the latter the
 229 stress state in the plastic zone. The resistance parameters are duplicated for the two-different peak
 230 and residual criteria: m_{bp} , s_p , a_p , m_{bres} , s_{res} , a_{res} . Peak parameters can be determined by using the
 231 GSI referring to the initial conditions of the rock mass, whilst the residual ones to a suitably
 232 reduced GSI (GSI_{res}) (Oreste, 2014).

233 In order to deal with the study of the conditions of the rock mass in the plastic zone, the criterion
 234 of residual failure of Hoek and Brown can be locally linearized by deriving it from the minimum
 235 principle stress σ_3 , which is the radial stress σ_r :

$$236 \quad \frac{d\sigma_{1,lim}}{d\sigma_3} = 1 + a_{res} \cdot m_{bres} \cdot \left(m_{bres} \cdot \frac{\sigma_3}{\sigma_{ci}} + s_{res} \right)^{a_{res}-1} \quad (7)$$

237 This derivative allows to directly obtain the apparent residual friction angle $\varphi_{res,app}$ of the rock
 238 mass, according to the existing minimum stress σ_3 :

$$239 \quad \sin\varphi_{res,app} = \frac{a_{res} \cdot m_{bres} \cdot \left(m_{bres} \cdot \frac{\sigma_3}{\sigma_{ci}} + S_{res}\right)^{a_{res}-1}}{a_{res} \cdot m_{bres} \cdot \left(m_{bres} \cdot \frac{\sigma_3}{\sigma_{ci}} + S_{res}\right)^{a_{res}-1} + 2} \quad (8)$$

240 The numerical procedure for defining the characteristic curve of the tunnel occurs is as follows
 241 (Oreste, 2014):

242 1. Calculation of the radial stress at the plastic radius (σ_{Rpl}): if this value is less than 0, no plastic
 243 zone is created around the tunnel; if it is greater than zero, a plastic zone is created for pressures
 244 inside the tunnel (p) lower than σ_{Rpl} ; the evaluation of σ_{Rpl} occurs by solving the following
 245 equation numerically:

$$246 \quad p_0 - \sigma_{Rpl} = \frac{\sigma_{ci}}{2} \cdot \left(m_{bp} \cdot \frac{\sigma_{Rpl}}{\sigma_{ci}} + S_p\right)^{\alpha_p} \quad (9)$$

247 2. In the presence of a plastic zone, we proceed with a finite difference method dividing the rock
 248 at the outline of the tunnel in concentric rings. Starting from the tunnel outline, where the radial
 249 stress is equal to the applied internal pressure (p), the stress is increased radially by a small
 250 amount of $\Delta\sigma_r$ value at each ring, until the σ_{Rpl} value is reached. At each value of $\sigma_{r,i}$, the
 251 corresponding value of $\sigma_{\theta,i}$ is used, employing the residual failure criterion of Hoek and Brown;
 252 3. By replacing in Equation 6 the term $(\sigma_{\theta} - \sigma_r)$ derived from the criterion of residual failure of
 253 Hoek and Brown:

$$254 \quad \sigma_{\theta} - \sigma_r = \sigma_1 - \sigma_3 = \sigma_{ci} \cdot \left(m_{bres} \cdot \frac{\sigma_3}{\sigma_{ci}} + S_{res}\right)^{a_{res}} \quad (10)$$

255 and transforming the equation obtained in incremental terms, the following expression is
 256 obtained:

$$\frac{\sigma_{r,i+1}-\sigma_{r,i}}{r_{i+1}-r_i} = \frac{\sigma_{ci} \cdot \left(m_{bres} \cdot \frac{(\sigma_{r,i+1}+\sigma_{r,i})/2}{\sigma_{ci}} + s_{res} \right)^{a_{res}}}{(r_{i+1}+r_i)/2} - \gamma \quad (11)$$

which allows to obtain all the values of r_{i+1} useful for determining the distances of the lateral surfaces of the concentric rings, comprised between the outline of the tunnel and the plastic radius R_{pl} ; this procedure also allows to obtain the value of the plastic radius R_{pl} ;

4. Starting then from the plastic radius backwards towards the tunnel contour, the deformation problem is solved. Knowing the stress state in all the concentric rings, the value of the radial displacement u is obtained on each surface of the concentric rings on the basis of the following differential equation valid for the plastic field under axisymmetric conditions:

$$\frac{du}{dr} = \frac{(1-\nu^2)}{E_r} \cdot \left[(\sigma_r - p_0) \cdot \left(1 - N_\psi \cdot \frac{\nu}{1-\nu} \right) + (\sigma_\theta - p_0) \cdot \left(N_\psi - \frac{\nu}{1-\nu} \right) \right] - N_\psi \cdot \frac{u}{r} \quad (12)$$

where: $N_\psi = \frac{1+\text{sen}\psi}{1-\text{sen}\psi}$

ψ is the dilatancy expressed in radians (dilatancy is an angle that can vary between 0 and the residual friction angle of the material);

ν is the Poisson ratio of the rock mass;

E_r is the elastic modulus of the rock mass in the plastic field (it can be evaluated referring to the value of GSI_{res}).

5. This differential equation is also transformed into incremental terms in order to be able to use it in the adopted finite difference method;

6. The dilation angle ψ is changed at each concentric ring, determining it as a percentage value of $\varphi_{res,app}$ evaluated through equation 9, where for σ_3 the mean radial stress at the specific i -th ring is considered:

$$\sigma_3 = \frac{(\sigma_{r,i+1}+\sigma_{r,i})}{2} \quad (13)$$

278 Once the outline of the tunnel is reached, it is possible, therefore, to obtain the radial displacement
279 u_R to be associated with the acting internal pressure p . The pairs of values $p - u_R$ allow to trace
280 the characteristic curve of the tunnel, considering the weight of the rock material present in the
281 plastic zone. A simplified sketch of the plastic zone for the case considered in this paper is shown
282 in Fig. 3.

283 **RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

284 The proposed solution was adopted in relation to a tunnel built in the Alps in metamorphic rocks
285 such as calcareous schists with a GSI of 35 ($GSI_{res} = 35$). The general geology of the area comprises
286 zones of contact between units of the continental crust and units preserving the characters of
287 oceanic crust. The unit where the tunnel is designed consists of a crystalline basement and limited-
288 strength permo-mesozoic metasediments mainly micascists and calcareous schists. The initial
289 section consists of calcareous schists then a gneiss with massive-to-foliated structure is
290 encountered.

291 This tunnel was assumed to be circular with an equivalent radius of 5m. The average overburden
292 was assumed as 170m ($p_0 = 5\text{MPa}$). The parameters of the rock mass are assumed as following:

- 293 • σ_{ci} of the intact rock is 60MPa;
- 294 • $m_i = 12$;
- 295 • disturbance factor $D = 1$;
- 296 • angle of dilatancy ψ equal to the angle of residual friction (associated flow rule assumption);
- 297 • Poisson ratio, ν , equal to 0.3.

298 On the basis of these data, the following parameters have been estimated:

- 299 • elastic module $E = 1635\text{MPa}$;

- 300 • parameter of resistance m_b equal to 0.115;
- 301 • parameter of resistance s equal to 2×10^{-5} ;
- 302 • parameter of resistance $a = 0.519$;
- 303 • the unit weight γ of the rock was evaluated at 30 kN/m^3 .

304 Fig. 4 shows the CCs of the tunnel, in the radial displacement range between 0.05 and 0.25m. The
305 curves referring to three cases are shown:

- 306 1. Case 1: Without considering the weight of the rock in the plastic zone (black continues
307 line);
- 308 2. Case 2: Considering the weight of the rock in the plastic zone according to the calculation
309 procedure illustrated in this article (grey dashed line);
- 310 3. Case 3: Considering the additional load due to the weight of the plasticized rock, according
311 to the conservative approach of Hoek and Brown (1980) and Panet (1995) (black dotted
312 line).

313 In the same figure, the reaction line of the lining is shown in black, consisting of a 25cm thick
314 fiber-reinforced sprayed concrete lining. Assuming an average elastic modulus during the setting
315 time equal to 10000MPa, a stiffness, k , of the lining is obtained equal to 105MPa/m, which
316 provides the slope to the reaction line. The load on the lining is obtained from the intersection of
317 the reaction line with the characteristic curve:

- 318 1. Case 1: 1.57MPa
- 319 2. Case 2: 1.62MPa
- 320 3. Case 3: 1.87MPa

321 It can be noted that the solution proposed in this article leads to an increase in load on the linings
322 of 3.2% due to the weight of the rock in the plasticized zone, while the simplified solution
323 considers an additional load equal to the weight of the rock multiplied by the thickness of the
324 plastic zone (case 3) leading to a considerable increase of 19.1% of the original load (case 1).

325 Figure 5 shows the trend of the plastic zones for case 1 (absence of weigh of the rock) and case 2
326 (proposed solution). In case 3, the trend coincides with case 1. It can be seen that the proposed
327 solution leads to a noticeable increase of the plastic radius until reaching a value of 29.4m for
328 internal pressure p equal to 0, compared to 19.4m of the case 1.

329 The proposed solution of the convergence-confinement method, therefore, provides vertical loads
330 slightly higher than the original ones, however with a significant increase in the thickness of the
331 plastic zone with respect to the case a) (without considering the weight of the rock inside the plastic
332 zone).

333 Three different load conditions on the lining have been studied from the three cases examined in
334 Fig. 4:

- 335 • condition a) refers to the presence of the same load in the crown and on the sides of the tunnel,
336 without considering the effect of the rock's own weight in the plastic zone (case 1);
- 337 • condition b) with the vertical load obtained from the proposed calculation procedure (modified
338 by Oreste, 2014) (case 2) considering the weight of the rock in the plastic zone and the
339 horizontal load without considering the weight of the rock in this zone (case 1);
- 340 • condition c) considering the simplified method of Hoek and Brown (1980) to determine the
341 effect of the weight of the rock in the plastic zone at the crown (case 3, simplified method) and
342 the horizontal load without considering the weight of the rock (case 1).

343 Figure 6 shows the trend of the bending moments along the development of half of the support
344 (starting from the center of the inverted arch up to the center of the crown) by applying the loads
345 as described above:

- 346 • Condition a): 1.57MPa in the vertical direction (case 1) and 1.57MPa in the horizontal one
347 (case 1);
- 348 • Condition b): 1.62MPa in the vertical direction (case 2) and 1.57MPa in the horizontal one
349 (case 1);
- 350 • Condition c): 1.87MPa in the vertical direction (case 3) and 1.57MPa in the horizontal one
351 (case 1);

352 These results were obtained using the hyperstatic reaction method (see Oreste, 2007; Do et al.
353 2014a; 2014b; Oreste et al., 2018a and 2018b for more details). This method provides for the
354 subdivision of the support into one-dimensional elements placed in succession, so as to represent
355 its entire development. The connection points between the elements are called nodes and on them
356 the springs simulating the interaction of the support with the rock face, both in the normal direction
357 and in the shear direction, are anchored. The loads acting on the support are represented with nodal
358 forces and the solution of the problem consists in obtaining the displacements of the nodes of a
359 support structure subjected to vertical and horizontal loads. Once the nodal displacements have
360 been obtained along the structure it is then possible to obtain the trend of the bending moments
361 and of the normal forces, useful for verifying the static conditions of the support. The following
362 data were used in the calculation:

- 363 • Stiffness of the normal interaction springs K_n : 490.5MN/m;
- 364 • Stiffness of the shear interaction springs K_s : 245.2MN/m;
- 365 • Limit strength of the elastic-plastic behavior of the normal springs F_n : 0.26 MN;

- 366 • Cohesion of the support-rock interface: 0.2MPa;
- 367 • Friction angle at the support-rock interface: 25°.

368 Because of the non-symmetry of the applied load, bending moments appear along the lining, which
369 reaches maximum values in the center of the invert, in the center of the crown and in the middle
370 of the side wall of the tunnel. These maximum bending moments, together with the values of the
371 normal force (Fig. 7) in correspondence with the same points at maximum moment, allow to derive
372 the internal stresses developing in the sprayed concrete linings. By comparing the maximum
373 internal stresses acting in the sprayed concrete with the strength of the sprayed concrete, it will be
374 possible to verify whether the hypotheses on the thickness of the lining and on the quality of the
375 sprayed concrete are compatible with the stability of the tunnel.

376 The analysis of the results shown in Fig. 6 allows to verify how the load condition c), which is
377 based on the evaluation of the vertical load in a simplified way, would lead to an overestimation
378 of the maximum bending moments of 600% with respect to the load condition b), for which the
379 evaluation of the vertical load was performed using the proposed calculation method. In the load
380 condition a), the bending moments are zero, thanks to the symmetry of load in the two directions
381 (vertical and horizontal). With regard to the normal forces (figure 7), a constant value is detected
382 along the support in the load condition a); in the load condition of b) the maximum normal force
383 is 3.2% higher than the value of the load condition a); finally, in the condition of load c) the
384 maximum normal force is about 19% higher than that found in the load condition a) and about
385 15% with respect to that obtained under load condition b). It can be noted that the simplified
386 methods, proposed for the determination of vertical load due to the weight of the plastic rock band,
387 lead to a sensible overestimation of the maximum bending moments in the support and a minor
388 overvaluation even of the maximum normal forces.

389 **ANALYSIS OF THE LINING-TUNNEL INTERACTION USING THE OBTAINED**
390 **CONVERGENCE-CONFINEMENT CURVES OF A BASE TUNNEL**

391 Considering the two convergence-confinement curves at the crown and for the sides of the tunnel
392 that can be obtained from the indicated procedure (Fig. 8A), there is a link load-displacement
393 characterizing the perimeter of the tunnel in the crown point and at the sides, based on the behavior
394 of the rock mass present at the boundary of the tunnel. It is also possible to determine the behavior
395 of a supporting structure in a simplified manner on the basis of its axial and flexural stiffness,
396 referring to the studies by Einstein and Schwartz (1979). By combining the two behaviors (of the
397 tunnel and of the supporting lining) it is possible to reach the exact determination of the actual
398 loads acting in the crown and at the sides of the tunnel, the displacements shown by the lining and
399 finally the bending moments and the normal forces that they develop along the support structure.
400 In this way it is possible to make an initial hypothesis about the type and size of the support
401 structure and then verify whether it is able to resist the bending moments and the normal forces
402 induced inside it. More specifically, referring to the work of Einstein and Schwartz (1979), it is
403 possible for the absence of sliding between the support and the rock wall (no-slip case) to obtain
404 the following equations of the support displacements at the crown (u_{crown}) and at the sides (u_{sides})
405 of the tunnel:

$$406 \quad u_{crown} = \frac{(d \cdot \sigma_{R,crown} - e \cdot \sigma_{R,sides})}{2 \cdot (d^2 - e^2) \cdot E} \cdot R \cdot (1 + \nu) \cdot \left\{ a_0^* \cdot \left[1 + \frac{1}{d} \cdot \left(\frac{\sigma_{R,sides} \cdot (d^2 - e^2)}{(d \cdot \sigma_{R,crown} - e \cdot \sigma_{R,sides})} - e \right) \right] - \left[1 - \frac{1}{d} \cdot \right. \right.$$

$$407 \quad \left. \left(\frac{\sigma_{R,sides} \cdot (d^2 - e^2)}{(d \cdot \sigma_{R,crown} - e \cdot \sigma_{R,sides})} - e \right) \right] \cdot h \right\} \quad (14)$$

$$408 \quad u_{sides} = \frac{(d \cdot \sigma_{R,crown} - e \cdot \sigma_{R,sides})}{2 \cdot (d^2 - e^2) \cdot E} \cdot R \cdot (1 + \nu) \cdot \left\{ a_0^* \cdot \left[1 + \frac{1}{d} \cdot \left(\frac{\sigma_{R,sides} \cdot (d^2 - e^2)}{(d \cdot \sigma_{R,crown} - e \cdot \sigma_{R,sides})} - e \right) \right] + \left[1 - \frac{1}{d} \cdot \right. \right.$$

$$409 \quad \left. \left(\frac{\sigma_{R,sides} \cdot (d^2 - e^2)}{(d \cdot \sigma_{R,crown} - e \cdot \sigma_{R,sides})} - e \right) \right] \cdot h \right\} \quad (15)$$

410 where: $\sigma_{R,crown}$ is the vertical load applied on the support at the crown;

411 $\sigma_{R,sides}$ is the horizontal load applied on the support at the sides;

412 R is the tunnel radius;

413 E and ν are respectively elastic modulus and Poisson modulus of the rock mass;

414
$$e = \frac{1}{2} \cdot (1 - a_0^*) - (1 - 6 \cdot a_2^* + 4 \cdot b_2^*);$$

415
$$d = \frac{1}{2} \cdot (1 - a_0^*) + (1 - 6 \cdot a_2^* + 4 \cdot b_2^*);$$

416
$$h = 4 \cdot (1 - \nu) \cdot b_2^* - 2 \cdot a_2^*;$$

417
$$f = \frac{1}{d} \cdot \left[\frac{\sigma_{R,sides} \cdot (d^2 - e^2)}{(d \cdot \sigma_{R,crown} - e \cdot \sigma_{R,sides})} - e \right];$$

418
$$a_2^* = \beta \cdot b_2^*;$$

419
$$\beta = \frac{(6 + F^*) \cdot C^* \cdot (1 - \nu) + 2 \cdot F^* \cdot \nu}{3 \cdot F^* + 3 \cdot C^* + 2 \cdot C^* \cdot F^* \cdot (1 - \nu)};$$

420
$$b_2^* = \frac{C^* \cdot (1 - \nu)}{2 \cdot [C^* \cdot (1 - \nu) + 4 \cdot \nu - 6 \cdot \beta - 3 \cdot \beta \cdot C^* \cdot (1 - \nu)]};$$

421
$$a_0^* = \frac{C^* \cdot F^* \cdot (1 - \nu)}{C^* + F^* + C^* \cdot F^* \cdot (1 - \nu)};$$

422
$$C^* = \frac{E \cdot R \cdot (1 - \nu_S^2)}{E_S \cdot A_S \cdot (1 - \nu^2)}$$
 (where A_S is the area of the lining section);

423
$$F^* = \frac{E \cdot R^3 \cdot (1 - \nu_S^2)}{E_S \cdot I_S \cdot (1 - \nu^2)}$$
 (where I_S is the inertia moment of the lining section).

424 Considering the convergence-confinement curve referred to the conditions at the crown (CCC

425 crown, obtained with the presence of the weight of the rock in the plastic zone), for each point

426 belonging to the CCC, the values of $\sigma_{R,crown}$ and u_{crown} are determined and are inserted in
 427 equation 14. From this equation $\sigma_{R,sides}$ is obtained and inserted in equation 15. Then, from this
 428 u_{sides} is obtained.

429 We proceed moving on the convergence-confinement curve referred to the crown conditions, until
 430 the pair of values $\sigma_{R,sides} - u_{sides}$ obtained from equations 14 and 15 are compatible with the
 431 convergence-confinement curve referred to the conditions at the sides (CCC sides, obtained
 432 without considering the weight in the plastic zone).

433 When compatibility is found, i.e. the correspondence between the behavior of the rock to the tunnel
 434 contour and the behavior of the support, the procedure stops and the values of the loads assessed
 435 on the crown $\sigma_{R,crown}$ and on the sides of the tunnel $\sigma_{R,sides}$ are used to determine bending
 436 moments (M) and normal forces along the support (N), by changing the angle θ which is the
 437 evaluation point in the circular support in the tunnel (see Fig. 8B):

$$438 \quad M = \frac{(d \cdot \sigma_{R,crown} - e \cdot \sigma_{R,sides}) \cdot R^2}{4 \cdot (d^2 - e^2)} \cdot (1 - f) \cdot (1 - 2 \cdot a_2^* + 2 \cdot b_2^*) \cdot \cos(2\theta) \quad (16)$$

$$439 \quad N = \frac{(d \cdot \sigma_{R,crown} - e \cdot \sigma_{R,sides}) \cdot R}{2 \cdot (d^2 - e^2)} \cdot [(1 + f) \cdot (1 - a_0^*) + (1 - f) \cdot (1 + 2 \cdot a_2^*) \cdot \cos(2\theta)] \quad (17)$$

440 CONCLUSIONS

441 During design of the supporting structures it is often necessary to evaluate the load applied by the
 442 rock mass to the outline of the tunnel, above all when using analytical methods of wide application
 443 such as the hyperstatic reaction methods. Generally, load estimation is performed using the
 444 convergence-confinement method, where the characteristic curve of the tunnel intersects with the
 445 support reaction line.

446 In the vertical direction, due to the loss of self-bearing of the rock present in the plastic zone, it is
447 necessary to consider the weight of the rock in the study of the evolution of stress and
448 deformations. In this work the methodology in which this aspect can be taken into consideration
449 has been presented. The numerical solution of the convergence-confinement method introduced
450 by Oreste (2014) has been modified to take into account the weight of the rock within the plastic
451 zone. In this way it is possible to obtain the modified characteristic curve in order to reach the
452 correct evaluation of the vertical load acting on the supporting work. As for the horizontal load,
453 however, it is possible to still refer to the original convergence-confinement curve, without taking
454 into account the weight of the plasticized rock.

455 The proposed solution was then applied to a case of a tunnel built in the Alps. Based on the
456 available data, the convergence-confinement curves of the tunnel were drawn and the loads acting
457 on the linings were evaluated. These loads were then used in the hyperstatic reaction method in
458 order to obtain the trend of the bending moments and of the normal forces along the development
459 of the lining.

460 From the study developed, it was possible to detect how the proposed solution allows to evaluate
461 vertical loads greater than a few percentage units compared to the case of weightlessness of the
462 plastic zone. The simplified solution considering an additional vertical load equal to the weight of
463 the rock by the thickness of the plastic zone, on the other hand, involves significant increases of
464 about 20%, which are not justifiable in practical terms. Moreover, from the example of calculation
465 carried out, it has been possible to identify a non-negligible increase in the value of the plastic
466 radius when considering the weight of the plastic zone. This increase in the plastic radius can be
467 of great interest due to the repercussions it may have in defining the length of the radial bolting in
468 the crown area.

469 Finally, a specific and quick procedure for the evaluation of the mechanical behavior of the support
470 of a base tunnel has been illustrated, referring to the convergence-confinement method and to the
471 method of analysis of a circular support by Einstein and Schwartz (1979). This procedure starts
472 from determining the two convergence-confinement curves of the tunnel (relative to the crown
473 zone, considering the weight of the plastic zone, and to the lateral areas, without considering the
474 weight of the plastic rock). More specifically, for each point of the convergence-confinement
475 curves of the crown zone (CCC crown) the values of the horizontal load and of the horizontal
476 displacement of the support at the sides of the tunnel are evaluated, compatible with the mechanical
477 behavior of the support. The procedure continues until this pair of values is compatible with the
478 convergence-confinement curves of the lateral zone of the tunnel, i.e. until the stress and
479 deformation analysis of the rock mass is compatible with the stress and deformation analysis of
480 the supporting structure. At that point it is possible to obtain the actual loads (vertical and
481 horizontal) acting on the supporting lining and, therefore, the trend of the bending moments and
482 of the normal forces along the development of the supporting structure.

483 **DISCLAIMER**

484 BASF is not involved in any form with the research presented in this paper and it is only the current
485 affiliation of one of the authors.

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568

569 **FIGURE CAPTION**

570 **Fig 1. Stresses on element ABCD in polar coordinate.**

571 **Fig. 2. (a) Schematic representation of the body forces at the tunnel roof. b) Graphical**
572 **demonstration of the ground response.**

573 **Fig. 3. Schematic representation of the tunnel with radius, R , of 5m with an overburden**
574 **pressure, p_0 , of 5MPa excavated in a rock with GSI_{peak} of 35 and UCS, σ_{ci} , of 60MPa showing**
575 **a plastic radius R_{pl} of 7.3m without considering the weight effect (not to scale).**

576 **Fig. 4. Convergence-confinement curves of the tunnel analyzed in the three considered cases**

577 **Fig. 5. Trend of the plastic radius of the tunnel as the internal pressure changes for case 1**
578 **(weightlessness of the rock in the plastic area) and case 2 (proposed solution).**

579 **Fig. 6. Trend of the bending moments along half of the support obtained with the hyperstatic**
580 **reaction method, applying the vertical and horizontal loads derived from the analysis with**
581 **the method of the characteristic curves and the solution proposed in this work.**

582 **Fig. 7. Trend of normal forces along half the support obtained by the hyperstatic reaction**
583 **method, applying the vertical and horizontal loads derived from the analysis with the method**
584 **of the characteristic curves and the solution proposed in this work.**

585 **Fig. 8. A). Procedure for the determination of the load values on the support ($\sigma_{R,crown}$ and**
586 **u_{crown}) from the convergence-confinement curve referred at the condition at crown (CCC**
587 **crown) and from that referred at the condition at sides (CCC sides). Key: p is the internal**
588 **pressure in the tunnel; u is the radial displacement of the tunnel wall; p_0 is the natural**
589 **lithostatic load at the tunnel depth; p_{cr} is the internal pressure below which a plastic region**

590 at the tunnel contour is formed; $\sigma_{R,crown}$ and $\sigma_{R,sides}$ vertical load acting on the support
591 respectively at the crown and at sides; u_{crown} and u_{sides} are the displacement support
592 respectively at the zone of crown and sides; B) Contact stresses at lining-rocks interface.

B

